

Activity report: COMET does Be Curious Public Engagement 2024

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Project overview

This report summarises the creation of outreach activities using a grant from the Centre for Observation and Modelling of Earthquakes, Volcanoes and Tectonics (COMET)¹ to support attendance at the annual Be Curious outreach event, run by the University of Leeds². We aimed to champion the breadth of COMET research by creating reusable public engagement activities that would provide a high-level overview of our work on earthquakes, volcanoes, tectonics, and earth observation. These included 3D printed and painted topographic models representing volcanoes, active faults and models of earth observation satellites; a laser cut map and jigsaw of Earth’s tectonic plates; a model of a strike-slip fault; and an erupting volcano. 3D printing and laser cutting was carried out at the HELIX³ innovation hub.

This report and associated outreach materials are available at:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12073233>

Outreach props

3D printing

Six topographic models were 3D printed at HELIX and painted by a local artist Molly Richardson (Moonwavey). We also 3D printed a vertically exaggerated Stromboli volcano for an erupting volcano activity, and several other props including fault block models to simulate different style of earthquake rupture.

The 3D topographic models were designed by clipping and exporting the Copernicus 30 m digital elevation model using the *DEMto3D* plugin⁴ for QGIS. These were then imported into Bambu Studio to prepare the model files for printing. Default settings were used with a 0.2 mm layer height. Models were printed on a Bambu Lab X1 Carbon 3D Printer at HELIX and print times ranged from 1–6 hours. Models were mostly printed using a white PLA filament, which was preferred for painting by the artist. A satellite image of each model was provided to the artist so that the predominant colours and key details could be matched when painting.

¹The Centre for Observation and Modelling of Earthquakes, Volcanoes and Tectonics (COMET) delivers cutting-edge science in Earth Observation, Tectonics and Volcanism. Through the integrated application and development of EO data, ground-based measurements, and geophysical models, COMET studies earthquakes and volcanoes, and the hazards they pose. The services, facilities, data and long-term underpinning research in EO science and geohazards that we produce benefit the wider community of environmental scientists, while helping the UK and other countries to prepare for, and respond rapidly to, earthquakes and eruptions. COMET brings together leading scientists across the British Geological Survey (BGS) and 8 UK partner universities, including the University of Leeds .

² <https://www.leeds.ac.uk/becurious>

³ <https://digitaleducation.leeds.ac.uk/helix/>

⁴ <https://demto3d.com/en/ayuda/>

3D Printing the island of Montserrat at HELIX, University of Leeds.

Example 3D printed and painted topographic models with laser engraved labels.

Laser cutting

A Laserscript LS6840 laser cutter at HELIX was used to produce wooden and acrylic props. Signage for the stall and for each topographic model was engraved onto 1.5 mm plywood and then cut out. A world map was engraved with tectonic plates⁵ overlaid, which were first simplified in QGIS to smooth the lines. A ruler was also designed as a give-away item on the stall using an online Ruler Generator⁶ and then adding logos and text. Laser cutting required experimentation with the engraving and cutting speeds to minimise the time required for each prop, whilst ensuring detail was captured without burning the wood. The world map with tectonic plates took approximately 15 minutes to engrave and cut on 1.5 mm plywood, and the rulers took approximately 30 seconds each and were cut in batches. Thicker wood would be more durable but requires longer cutting times. The laser cutter was also used to cut green and blue acrylic shapes including a river for a strike-slip earthquake landscape prop.

Laser cutting at HELIX.

Laser engraved and cut signage and props, including a world map with tectonic plate lines and a giveaway branded ruler.

⁵ <https://hub.arcgis.com/datasets/5f01bc7f78d74498aa942455fcd0dc10/explore?showTable=true>

⁶ <https://robddd.github.io/VectorRuler/>

Colouring sheets

Three colouring sheets were designed by local artist Molly Richardson (Moonwavey) to capture the three key elements of our stall. These were distributed on a maker space table near our stall for participants to colour and take away.

A4 Colouring sheets.

Be Curious event

The Be Curious outreach day ran 10–4 pm on the 18th May 2024, with a quiet hour 10–11 am. We had five volunteers from the project team helping on the stall throughout the day.

Activities and props

1. Display screen showing the seismic event monitor⁷.
 2. Laser cut world map with tectonic plates.
 3. Two-piece painted Piqiang fault, China, showing a 3 km offset of the mountain topography.
 4. Three Fault blocks⁸ to simulate strike-slip, normal, and reverse faults.
 5. Laser cut strike-slip offset landscape for interpretation.
 6. Playdough block of 'lava' deposit layers for participants to core using a clear tube.
 7. 3D printed models and satellites. Including a five-piece Cayambe Volcano jigsaw puzzle.
 8. Lava samples including floating pumice.
 9. An erupting model of Stromboli volcano. Participants added vinegar to a mixture of baking soda, food colouring, washing up liquid and water.
 10. A giant satellite image floor map with a series of features to find provided by Jacob Connolly and SatSchool⁹.
 11. Printed colouring sheets on a large table opposite our stall.
 12. Printed activity cards for participants to say what they liked or learned on the stall.
 13. Participants were offered a laser cut ruler and a sweet after they had engaged with the stall.
- We also had giveaway colouring sheets and pencils.

⁷ <https://www.iris.edu/app/eqc/>

⁸ Fault Block by mhoeckstra on Thingiverse: <https://www.thingiverse.com/thing:691147>

⁹ <https://satschool-outreach.github.io/>

Activity Card

Return me for a gift

Please list a few words or draw a sketch following your visit to our stand
We'd love to hear what you learned!

Satellites

Earthquakes

Volcanoes

COMET

We use **satellite** measurements alongside ground-based observations and geophysical models to study **earthquakes** and **volcanoes**, and help understand the **hazards** they pose.

<https://comet.nerc.ac.uk> @NERC_COMET

Activity card and business card size COMET promotional card.

The COMET stall at Be Curious

Impact

Participation at Be Curious was designed to showcase the diversity of research within the University of Leeds and COMET, and to inspire interest in the research activities. Our activities were designed to cover all age ranges but were primarily targeted towards the expected audience of primary school aged children.

- We received great feedback from the event organiser and from participants who were interested in all elements of the stall.
- Example comments: *'amazing', 'fun', 'very interesting', 'I learnt a lot about Earthquakes and Volcanoes'*
- Children erupted our model volcano over 50 times, located features on the giant satellite image, learnt about earthquake styles, handled volcanic lava, and discovered the monitoring capabilities of satellites.
- The team of post graduate researchers supporting the stall had the opportunity to speak about their research and why it is important to study volcanoes and earthquakes.
- The project leader was trained to use the 3D printers and laser cutter in HELIX.
- The outreach materials were designed to be reusable and surplus consumables are available for use in subsequent outreach events. We expect the materials will be used at Be Curious again in 2025.

Examples of the colouring sheets left by participants.

Examples of completed activity cards.

Be Curious COMET Public Engagement

C. Scott Watson with support from: Jessica Payne, Alice Hopkins, Eilish O'Grady, John Condon, Jacob Connolly, and Rachel Bilsland.

COMET, School of Earth and Environment, University of Leeds, UK. COMET is the NERC Centre for the Observation and Modelling of Earthquakes, Volcanoes and Tectonics, a partnership between UK Universities and the British Geological Survey.

Be Curious

Annual public engagement event at the University of Leeds.
~2000 visitors, typically families with young children.

Why do we study volcanoes and earthquakes?

Aim: champion the breadth of COMET research by creating reusable public engagement activities that would provide a high-level overview of our work on earthquakes, volcanoes, tectonics, and earth observation.

Funded by a COMET Outreach Fund grant (£1,410)

Public Engagement Props

3D Printing Laser Cutting & Engraving Activities

- Earthquakes/ Tectonics**
- Display screen showing a seismic monitor (EarthScope Earthquake Channel).
 - Laser cut world map/ jigsaw with tectonic plates.
 - Two-piece painted Pijiang fault, China (3 km offset of topography).
 - 3D printed fault blocks to simulate strike-slip, normal, and reverse faults.
 - Laser cut strike-slip offset landscape for interpretation.
- Volcanoes**
- An erupting model of Stromboli volcano. Participants added vinegar to a mixture of baking soda, food coloring, washing up liquid and water.
 - Lava samples including floating pumice.
 - 3D printed and painted models, including a Cayambe Volcano jigsaw puzzle.
 - Playdough block of 'lava' deposit layers for participants to 'core'.
- Earth observation**
- A giant satellite image floor mat (SatSchool) with a list of features to find.
 - 3D printed satellites.
- Supporting**
- Coloring sheets and pencils on a large table opposite our stall.
 - Printed activity cards for participants to say what they liked & learned.
 - Handouts: laser cut ruler and sweets after they had engaged with the stall.

On the Day

Colouring sheets

Impact

- Engaged with 100s of children and families.
- Great interest and feedback
- Training: laser cutter and 3D printer at HELIX (University of Leeds).
- Public engagement experience for post graduate researchers.
- Reusable outreach materials. Contact Scott if you would like to use them.
- Full project report and downloadable materials will be linked from the COMET website.
- We are waiting for the official attendance statistics and photographs.

Example Comments & Feedback

Amazing Fun Very interesting

Poster summarising the outreach that was presented at the COMET Annual Meeting 2024.

Budget

The project budget was provided by the COMET EDI and Outreach Fund.

Cost	Budgeted	Actual expenditure	Notes
3D printed models	£150	£39	Materials provided by HELIX
Artist painting of 3D printed models	£660	£790	Included two additional models to the six originally budgeted
Laser cutting	£0	£0	Materials provided by HELIX
Colouring sheet design	£0	£150	Not originally budgeted
Printing costs	£80	£103.80	
Additional items to support the stall and activities including: Baking soda (2.5 kg), spirit vinegar (10l), food colouring, washing up liquid, erupting volcano tray and jerry can, funnel, beakers, duct tape, glue, string, play dough, clear thick straws, trays, kitchen roll, baby wipes, colouring pencils, sweets, and two large storage boxes.	£320	£327.52	
Travel and subsistence for stall volunteers	£90	£0	Be Curious provided £5 lunch vouchers
Total	£1,410	£1,410	